

NAMES OF PLACES WITH A NATURAL-GEOGRAPHICAL BASIS ENVIRONMENTAL FUNCTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the ecological functions of the place names that have a natural-geographic wand in the Fergana Valley. A brief summary of the names of some places is expressed.

The introductory part. In analyzing the current state and variation of landscapes typical for the Fergana Valley, it is possible to use Geographic Names that reflect the existing landscape types. The geographical names associated with the type of landscape from the specific natural geographic features of the territory, give information about the past of these natural objects, the change and the current state of them as a result of the influence of anthropogen, in addition to the adresic function, which is the main function of Geographic Names, also performs an ecological function.

It is known that changes in natural landscapes are influenced by various processes. Especially as a result of economic activity of people, changing landscape types are observed in densely distributed, economically developed regions of the population. In this regard, it should be noted that changes in natural landscapes, specific manifestations are caused not only by the influence of economic activity on people, but also by natural processes occurring on the ground (tectonic movements, wind,

precipitation, hot-cold, etc.) the result will also be.

As a result of these processes, various forms, geographical objects representing the natural features of the place, are widely distributed around the world. However, when studying them geographically, attention is paid only to the change of the object in the influence of external forces, its specific shape, aesthetic aspects. Little attention is paid to such aspects as the fact that the geographic object and its name correspond to today's natural-social features. In addition, such geographical names as the above become the image, embodiment, image of the place, creating geoconception that characterize its unique natural features.

The main part. The Fergana Valley is characterized by the fact that the words steppe, sand, desert are widely used in the composition of Geographic, denoting the landscape structure and features of the place. In the researches, the boundaries of these landscape zones are also changing and it was determined from the geographical nomenclature.

Usually the steppe is a geographical term used in relation to the "unpaved, waterless desert".

In natural geography, the steppe is said to be a natural zone, a region that is located in the North relative to the desert, richer than in the flora and fauna. The names of places related to the steppe are repeated in the form of Vurugdashi, Steppe, steppe village, steppe neighborhood, steppe Pandigon, steppe mill, steppe, steppe Hasan, Archer, Ghanidasht, Khoshidasht. The areas of today's geographical distribution of the name areal are Besharik, Stony, Kuva, Izkankan, Baghdad, Namangan, Dograkurgan, Rishton, Uzbekistan, Uchkoprik districts, and are mainly suitable for areas where the desert and steppe landscapes are scattered. However, this steppe zone is mastered with the help of powerful irrigation systems. As a result of the transfer of all the major channels in the valley from this area, this type of landscape was completely finished at the end of the last century and in place were built Anthropoid landscapes. Also, the names of places with the participation of the "sand" suffix associated with the landscape structure of the place in the valley are chalk, Akkum, Karakum, Kumbosti, sand, Kumarik, Kumguzar, Kumkishlag. In this regard, it should also be taken into account that the occurrence of these place names can occur on the basis of the legislation of relative negativity. According to him, when naming a place, the name of natural and social objects, which are relatively rare for this territory, attracts everyone's attention, is chosen. As a rule, with a sandy area, other soils are scattered, in the border areas these names are many there. Therefore, these names are the most common in the districts bordering the Central Fergana, sometimes even after the address zone. For example, such as Karakum (Kuva district), Kumguzar (Bulukbashi district). It is possible to observe that the regions where the geographical names are distributed, in which the words Boz, salty, desert, forest, grass, desert, which provide

information about the natural-landscape conditions of the place, are also involved, do not correspond to the regions where today's natural landscapes are distributed. In the villages known as steppe-Yunus (Baghdad district), steppe, Choligulistan (Rishton district), the components reminiscent of the desert landscape are almost not met today. Under the influence of human economic activity, the area of desert landscapes in Central Fergana is also sharply reduced from year to year. In most of these places, natural steppes and sand dunes are almost not encountered. There is a problem of preserving these landscapes as a monument of nature. Because the area of the nature monument "Yazyovon steppes" is shrinking from year to year.

In the Fergana Valley, geographic names representing the terrestrial structure of the place are common. Such geographical names associated with the structure, levels of the terrain relief-oronyms include not only mountain, (stone) adir, Heights and hills, but also negative forms of the relief - valleys, Gorges, ravines, shadows, groove-outs, as well as Plains, low - plains. Over time, the release of the object can change, but the name that expresses the same release will remain. This group can also include geographic names beginning with the word "Stone" (Sang). These names were used as the common name of the stone cobwebs – solid Mountaineers in the composition, or separately Standing Rock. Names of neighborhoods and villages such as tashabad, Tashbulak, Tashlak, Tashlaktepa, Tashkurgan, Tashhuvuz, Polvontos, Sanglak, Sangzor were recorded and the stone soy toponym contained in them was used as a binder. It is known that the withdrawal of the sea from the Fergana Depression occurred at the end of the Tertiary period, the mountains in the Paleozoic era, the Adirs in the Mesozoic era, the plains in the Quaternary period turned

into droughts. As a result of the ascent of the taiga foothills in the Valley, groundwater moved towards its central part, as a result of which there were marshes and marshes. In the valley, the population was mainly engaged in livestock farming, irrigated farming and mountaineering. It was observed that after the Half-Life of the population engaged in cattle breeding began to live, they fell into the lower parts of the Valley and prepared for themselves a special place for wintering. Convenient places for such a population to live were the hills and the surrounding areas. As a result, it is possible that the population mastered the lands around the hills and built their settlements on these lands initially in the form of temporary "fortifications" (such as in the form of fortifications, hillocks, sandstorms, steppes, jargons, Spruce), and then in the form of villages. The name of the geographical objects involved in the "top" survey is repeated more than 60 times in the Fergana Valley. To them are Aziztepa, Arabtepa, Arziktepa, Ashqoltepa, chalk, honeycomb, Yortepa, Zindontepa, Kamoltepa, Kitkontepa, Mingtepa, Munchoqtepa, Aktepa, Simtepa, Sochtepa, Surxtepa, Tashtepa, Tepekürg, Uchtepa, Şahartepa, Kızıltepa. In the Valley, Geographic Names formed by the so-called "Pit" (yor, yar), which reflect the negative relief properties of the place, are also common. The pit is a depth of different sizes, which is formed from the fact that these temporary flowing waters carved and washed the Earth. The pit is mostly formed from the soft rocks (lyoss, lysimon kumak), High Plains, much three along the slope of the foothills. The pit also means depth, lowness in toponymy in general. In the Valley, a pitcher was involved in the name of such geographical objects as Anorjar, Jamanjar, Jararik, Jarbashi, Jarmachit, jargon, jargon, Oqjar, Tagijar, Kyzyljar. In the Uychi District of Namangan region there are villages called Yortepa, Yorkurgan, Yortagi,

Yorkucha, Keskanoyor, Yangikurgon, Yorkishlak in Chust districts, Yorkishlak in Andijan region, Yorkishlak, Akyor, Kuyganyor, Fergana District of Fergana region, Yormozor, Yordon. When the territorial distribution of the Fergana Valley is considered with the help of field research, it is possible to observe that their today's distribution regions have changed little. It is possible to observe that such names are given to water bodies, settlements, landscape types. In particular, if the names of the Jarik, Tagijar are given to water objects, the names of Jamanjar, Vortex, Cartepa, Jarnami are given to landscape types, jargon, slang, jargon, Akjar, Uzbekqoq are given to settlements. The initial thoughts about the use of the combing function of these names are H.H.Hasanov, S.Karaev, N. It was given by such researchers as okhunov. The combing functions of these names have the opportunity, first of all, to use land and water resources in farming. Cartographic analysis of the territorial location of these names shows that they are located in the basins, sometimes in steep relief landscapes, in the high plains of the foothills, in the landscapes of the range of adiris, Taiga and adir, in the upper parts of conical spreads. From an administrative point of view, it can be seen that in the regions of Kosonsay, Uzbekistan, Besharik, Fergana, Pakhtaabad are given to many microtoponyms (fields, places, small ditches), except for large villages, counties. Such, from the point of view of the use of nature, it is desirable to use names that denote a negative form of release (low, low, deep) in the sense of the comb function, in the arrangement of settlements, industrial vatransportiz, except for rural areas. It can be noted that the Valley corresponds to the name of the form of relief in settlements called: Adirbobo, Pakanaadir, Chordara, Hawthorn, Belarus, belt, honeycomb or deep-pit, deep-pit cabinets with a deep-pit. Even in the

expression of the location of one population Punkt in relation to another population Punkt, the words high and low (lower, lower), from the general berk state of the Valley, many of the geographical names involved fly.

It is possible to observe that geographic objects bearing such names are widely distributed mainly in the high plains of the foothills and conical expanses, on the territory of the wreckage of the Adir horde. In particular, such as high, high Substituteboy, high spruce, high Beshkapa, high hornbeam, high rollers, High Valley, High rosehip, high Zarkaynar, high snowball, high Mangite, high Mindon, high Mirzaabad, high Moyan, high Rowan, High Navkent, high Taval, High Cross, High Suburban, High-Suburban, High-suburban. Such names are created in accordance with the law of the rows in the science of toponymic, and in the immediate vicinity of the villages it is possible to see the names of the place where the same village or city was built with the name of itself or with the addition of the words bottom (bottom) to it.

In the valley, the localities associated with the climate and meteorological characteristics of the place are also diverse. It includes Bogishamol, Terskay. In Turkic languages, the names formed by the expression, which means wind, also fly. The use of ku supplement in names such as Chorku

Peshku, Baku in the sense of the word is emphasized by researchers. In this regard, it is noteworthy that in the name of the largest cities of the Valley VA, the general geographical features of the Commonwealth are taken into account. The Kokand was originally recorded in the form of Khukand (Khuvakand) and Khukand in the works of "Hudud al-Alam", then Istakhriy, Ibn Havkal. H.Hasanov comments on Kokand as "the city of Khukand – wind, the city of sershamol". The second component of my toponym is " kand "(village), in the sense of the city. The fall of the sound D is a characteristic feature of the Uzbek language. The first part of the name sheep hu means "wind". So The Cuckoo means" the city of the wind".

Conclusion. In the Fergana Valley, the geographical names denoting the landscape structure and features of the place are distinguished by the fact that the words steppe, sand, steppe are widely used in their composition. In the researches, the boundaries of these landscape zones are also changing and it was determined from the geographical nomenclature. The ecological functions of the place names, which have a natural-geographic wand in the Fergana Valley, were covered, and the brief content of some place names was expressed.

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